

FATIGUE DAMAGE DETECTION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS USING THERMOSONICS TECHNIQUE

Xiaoyan Han¹, Ahsan Mian², and Golam Newaz²
Departments of Mechanical², and Electrical and Computer¹ Engineering
Wayne State University
Detroit, Michigan

ABSTRACT

The ‘thermosonics’ NDE technique is used for fatigue damage evaluation in graphite/epoxy composite samples. In this technique, a short pulse of sound wave is infused into the material that results in frictional heating at the crack surfaces. The heating at the damage zones reaches the sample surface by conduction, and thus the temperature of the surface in the crack location rises. This temperature rise is sufficient to be captured by an infrared (IR) camera. In this paper, the thermosonics technique is used for detecting fatigue damage in several notched and un-notched composite samples. The samples are first subjected to fatigue loading, and the fatigue tests are interrupted periodically so that the samples are tested for damage entities using thermosonics technique. The thermosonics images of the fatigued samples are collected at various cycles to demonstrate the damage progression with fatigue loads. In addition, a non-contact laser vibrometer is used to monitor the vibration pattern of a point on the sample during the thermosonics test to better understand the effect of the infused sound pulse at the damage zones.

KEYWORDS: composites, thermosonics, fatigue damage, infrared (IR) imaging, and NDE.

INTRODUCTION

Laminated composite plates have superior specific mechanical properties to mechanical properties of conventional metallic materials. Since they are fabricated by stacking unidirectional or woven plies, they have low delamination resistance. Low delamination resistance results in delamination cracks by slight impacts such as a tool drop or under cyclic loading. To improve this low reliability, identifications of delamination cracks in-service are required [1]. In addition, the composite laminates subjected to fatigue loading undergo succession of various forms of damage before complete failure. These damage mechanisms include matrix ply cracking [2-3], edge delamination [4-5], and local delaminations arising from matrix ply cracks [6-7]. To avoid catastrophic failure of practical laminated composite structures, a health monitoring system is one desirable approach for detecting damage initiation, progression, and accumulation due to such cyclic loadings. Over the years, various non-destructive evaluation (NDE) techniques such as X-ray radiography [8], ultrasonics C-scan [9, 10], thermography [11] etc. have been used for fatigue damage detection in different materials. All of the established NDE techniques require tremendous data and image processing that need a great deal of time. In addition, all of the established techniques cannot be used for detecting fatigue cracks in practical composite structures. In contrast, the newly developed NDE technique called ‘thermosonics’ [12, 13] is capable of imaging fatigue damage in materials within a few seconds and can be employed for applied structures.

The thermosonics technique is based on the heating at cracks or disbands in a material due to the applied sound wave into it. The heat is predominantly generated from friction of the contact surfaces when they rub onto each other during the application of the sound pulse [12-15]. For a surface crack, the heat appears at the surface immediately after the infusion of sound pulse, while it appears some time later for a subsurface crack as the heat reaches the surface by conduction from the crack location. For both cases, the hot zones become more smeared as time goes on due to heat diffusion. The effect appears to begin in a few milliseconds after the application of a sound pulse to the sample. Images showing temperature distribution on the surface of a sample during and aftermath of the sound pulse infusion are captured by an infrared (IR) camera. The images with 'hot spots' are then analyzed to identify potential damage in the sample. To prevent damage of the material, a softer material called 'coupling material' is used between the ultrasonic transducer gun and the sample. The thermosonics technique has already been used in detecting fatigue cracks in various isotropic metal materials such as aluminum, titanium, etc. However, the ability of the technique in detecting fatigue damage in composite materials is yet to be tested.

As mentioned earlier that the laminated composites subjected to cyclic loadings may contain damage in the form of matrix cracking followed by delamination [5-8]. In this paper, fatigue damage progression in various composites samples with circular holes detected using thermosonics technique is presented. In addition, two coupling materials such as leather and duct tape were used to understand the effect of coupling materials on the vibration spectrum and hence the intensity of heat generation at the damage zones. The vibration spectrum of a point on the sample was monitored and recorded by a non-contact laser vibrometer during the test.

MATERIALS

The composite material used in this study is consisted of woven $[(0/90)_{4s}]$ IM7 carbon fiber reinforced 5208 epoxy. Resin-transfer molding (RTM) process was used to manufacture the composite panels. The thickness and fiber volume fraction of each panel are nominally 3.0 mm and 0.55, respectively. A total of seven rectangular specimens were cut from a composite panel. The specimens are 25 mm wide and 216 mm long. Of the seven samples, four were unnotched and the remaining three are notched. The notched samples have a hole of 6.2 mm diameter at the geometric center.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Fatigue Tests

The samples were subjected to tension-tension fatigue tests at a stress ratio (R) of 0.1 with the maximum stress of 75% of the ultimate strength. The applied load was sinusoidal with a frequency of 5 Hz. For all of the samples, the tests were interrupted periodically and the samples were tested using thermosonics technique. The thermosonics images of the fatigued samples were collected at 0, 1000, 3000, and 13000 cycles. It is mentioned here that before conducting the fatigue tests, the failure load of a notched and an un-notched samples were determined using quasi-static tensile tests and were observed to be 490 MPa and 590 MPa, respectively. The reduction in failure stress for the notched sample is due to the initial delamination in the notch region attributed from the machining procedure. All tests were conducted in a 100 kN servo-hydraulic closed-loop testing machine under load control. Test machine actuator position and load for the static test were recorded with an automated data acquisition system.

Thermosonics Evaluation

The experimental set up for the thermosonics test is shown in Figure 2. Both ends of the sample were kept fixed while a low frequency (20 kHz) ultrasonic gun of 1.0 kW maximum power was placed on one of the fixed ends to infuse a short pulse of sound for 200 ms. The surface temperature of the sample was imaged by an infrared video camera that is operated in 3-5 μm region. The camera is operated by a control software, which triggers the camera and the ultrasonic excitation sequentially as well. The camera digitizes the video images with a 14-bit depth, and transmits them to the computer as a stream of 16-bit data. The entire tests were carried out using leather as a coupling material.

In the second part of the test, only one (sample #2) notched sample was used to understand the effect of coupling materials on IR images. In this study, two coupling materials such as leather and duct tape were used for comparison. A different ultrasonic gun of 40 kHz (a maximum power of 0.8 kW) was used to excite the sample for a duration of 150 ms. For every coupling material, IR images of the sample were captured and the out-of plane vibration spectrum was monitored near the hole at the same time using a non-contact laser vibrometer. The vibration data was acquired by a data acquisition software that operates on a separate computer. The vibrometer was triggered simultaneously with the ultrasonic gun and the camera by the camera control software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Damage Evaluation

Figure 2 shows a sequence of thermosonics images for a notched sample before the sample was subjected to fatigue. The images are taken during the 200 ms period of an acoustic pulse. Figures 2(a), 2(b), 2(c), and 2(d) represent the images at the beginning of the pulse, shortly after the beginning of the pulse, in the middle of the pulse, and after the pulse. The images show the heating progression and its diffusion away from the damage zones. The blurred appearance and the pixelation of the images result from the fact that they represent small areas selected from a wide-area 320x256 pixel image. It can be noted that the damage entities around the circular notch were attributed from the machining procedure of the sample.

To obtain the thermosonics images at various cycles, the fatigue tests were interrupted and the samples were removed from the MTS machine. After the samples were tested, they were reinserted into the machine and the fatigue cycles continued. The samples were then repeatedly removed from the tester and additional thermosonics images were captured. Figure 3 shows the thermosonics images for a notched sample (sample #4) at various load cycles. It is seen from the figures that some damage was present initially before the samples were subjected to cyclic loadings. This damage was attributed during the machining of the samples. As the cyclic loading progresses, the initial damage near the circular notch has propagated further. The possible damage mechanisms are predominantly delamination along with distributed matrix cracks [5-8, 17-20]. The thermosonics images for an unnotched sample at different load cycles are shown in Figure 4. It is observed that the damage areas increased with the fatigue load cycles as expected. In this case, damage seems to have started from the edge of the sample. This is due to the obvious reason that the samples had some initial damages at the edge while machining them from a large composite plate.

Effect of Coupling Materials

As mentioned earlier that leather and duct tape were used as coupling materials for this part of the study. Figures 5(a) and 5(b) show IR images near the hole of a notched sample (sample #2) for leather

and duct tape, respectively. The IR images shown here were captured near the end of 150 ms pulse duration. It is apparent from the figure that the thermal intensity in the hot areas (damage zones) generated by duct tape is much higher than the other case. The variations of signal intensity with frame number at a same coordinate point on the sample surface right below the hole is shown in Figure 6. This data was extracted from the IR images given in Figure 5 using an image processing software developed by our research group. In fact, signal intensity and frame number represent relative magnitudes of temperature and time, respectively. Thus, the plots in Figure 6 will be called as T-t (temperature-time) plot. As shape, nature, and relative magnitude of the curves are necessary for comparison, the calculation of absolute temperature is not required. It is mentioned earlier that the ultrasonic gun infuses sound pulse to the sample resulting in the frictional heat at the crack surfaces. The frictional heat reaches the sample surface by conduction. Since the IR camera and the ultrasonic gun are triggered simultaneously, the camera does not see the temperature rise in the damage region until the heat conducts to the surface. This phenomenon is clear in the T-t plots in Figures 6 where no temperature change is seen during the first several frames after the ultrasonic source is turned on. After then, temperature starts rising due to additional heating as the infusion of the sound pulse progresses. As the sound source is turned off after 150 ms, the temperature starts falling due to cooling down of the hot areas (damage zones). It is observed from the figure that the maximum thermal intensity (or temperature) in the case of leather is well below that generated using duct tape. This is due to the reason that the leather is a thicker and softer material, and hence it has absorbed a remarkable portion of the input sound energy.

For further understanding, a non-contact laser vibrometer was used to monitor the vibration pattern of a point on the surface (the location is shown in Figure 7) during the application of sound pulse. The plot in Figure 7(a) shows the out-of-plane velocity of a point right above the circular hole in the case of leather. Fast Fourier transform (FFT) of the entire time range of the data is depicted in Figure 7(b). Also shown in Figure 7 is the vibration spectrum of the same point while the pulse was applied through duct tape. It is clear that the vibration spectrum obtained from duct tape contains harmonics at different acoustic modes and the peak is attained at 40 kHz which is the frequency of the induced sound pulse. However, the vibration spectrum obtained using leather does not contain any harmonics other than the input frequency (40 kHz). The peak velocity attained by using duct tape (0.3932 mm/ms) is seen to be much higher than leather (0.0698). This again testifies that leather has absorbed dampened the infused pulse. The higher peak velocity of the damage locations and the presence of harmonics has contributed to the generation of higher heat energy in the case of duct tape, as was observed from the IR images.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented the ability of thermosonics technique to assess subsurface fatigue damage in advanced composite materials. In the thermosonics technique, a low frequency sound infusion in a sample leads to a friction energy generation at the faying surfaces of the fatigue damages. This localized heat energy diffuses to the surface of the sample which is imaged using an IR camera. Fatigue damage accumulation in both notched and unnotched samples was imaged as a function of load cycles number. By comparing two coupling materials, it is concluded that the duct tape is superior in generating higher thermal intensity which in turn gives greater details of the damage zones in composites.

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Figure 1 – Schematic Diagram of Thermosonics Technique

Figure 2 – Thermosonics Images (a) at the beginning of the pulse, (b) shortly after the beginning of the pulse, (c) in the middle of the pulse, and (d) after the pulse

Figure 3 – Thermosonics images for a notched specimen (sample #4) (a) at 0 cycle, (b) 3000 cycles, and (c) at 13000 cycles

Figure 4 – Thermosonics images for an un-notched sample at (a) 0 cycle, (b) 3000 cycles, and (c) 13000 cycles

(a) coupling material - leather

(b) coupling material – duct tape

Figure 5 – Thermosonics images for a notched specimen (sample #2) at 13000 cycles

Figure 6 – thermal intensity change with frame number

Figure 7 – vibration spectrum of a point on a notched sample above the hole (coupling material–leather)

Figure 8 – vibration spectrum of a point on a notched sample above the hole (coupling material–duct tape)